

**Exchange of methods in language teaching
Bektoshev Khudaynazar Shodmon o'g'li
is a student of group 301
of the Faculty of Foreign Philology
of Termiz State University**

Annotation: This article discusses the exchange of skills and methods of teachers of different countries and higher education institutions in language teaching.

Keywords: education system, teaching - methodical, pedagogical staff.

Currently, in our country, attention is being paid to young people and their provision with qualified education. in accordance with the priority tasks of socio-economic development, it was adopted in order to fundamentally revise the content of personnel training, to create the necessary conditions for the training of highly qualified specialists at the level of international standards. In the years of independence, based on the real demands of the economy and social life, great work was done on the modernization of the higher education system in our country, the introduction of modern forms and technologies of teaching, and the improvement of specialization areas for the training of specialists. At the same time, the results of the study of the current situation in the higher education system by the Working Group, formed on the basis of the order of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on October 8, 2016, show that the scientific and pedagogical potential in a number of higher education institutions is still at a low level remains, the teaching-methodical and information supply of the educational process does not meet modern requirements, the material and technical base needs to be systematically updated. It has been more than 2 years since the establishment of the educational inspection of the quality of education under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan. During the past period, the study of advanced foreign experiences in performing the tasks assigned to the inspection and the assessment of the quality of education in our country have been introduced. targeted work is being carried out. At the moment, measures are being taken to improve the advanced aspects of foreign pedagogy, to introduce new subjects into the curriculum, and to turn it into one of the most advanced pedagogies in the world. The work on improving the qualifications of pedagogues and scientific personnel by widely introducing advanced international experience into the educational process in the higher education system, establishing close cooperation relations with leading foreign scientific and educational institutions, is not being carried out at the required level. . Termiz State University has well-established international cooperation relations with foreign HEIs. to improve the professional skills of professors and teachers, to improve

the qualifications of pedagogical staff, as well as to improve their qualifications at foreign partner higher educational institutions, to receive master's and doctoral studies, as well as to undergo retraining and improvement of qualifications at the base higher educational institutions of our republic. In particular, at the Faculty of Foreign Philology of Termiz State University, Doctor of Philology, Professor Koroleva Vera Vladimirovna of Vladimir State University of Russia, conducts an interesting lesson for students of the Department of English Language Teaching.

While conducting classes on topics such as "Global English" and "Suitable course materials for ESP", he introduced students to the modern and unique features of the language teaching methodology, as well as the language teaching methodology at the university where he works. gave detailed insights about the scientific works he has carried out. Also, in order to increase the academic mobility of professors and teachers based on the memorandum between the universities, Vladimir State University teachers N.V. Mitiushina and senior teacher Y.N. Ionova are undergoing 2-week training at the Department of English Language Teaching Methodology of Termiz State University. The students, who have great impressions from the interesting activities, are satisfied with this visit and the lessons. At the same time, it was not only a novelty for students, but also a real exchange of methods and practice for teachers.

References

1. Richard J.C, Rogers T.S. Approaches and Methods in language Teaching/Cambridge university press,- 2010.
2. Djalolov J. В. Инглиз тили ўқитиш методикаси. Тошкент, 2010
3. Broughter G. Teaching English as a foreign language. 1996.
4. Кашина Е.Г. Традиции и инновации в методике преподавания Иностранного языка. САМАРА: Универс-групп, 2006. – 75 с.